

Some Aspects of Commercial Generation of Biogas from Common Wastes

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Biogas generation from different wastes have been widely reported¹. The laboratory experiments have also shown that recycling of sewage and plant biomass can be successfully implemented to generate biogas.

The pollution of the river Ganga and other rivers as well, arises due to discharge of domestic and industrial effluents without proper treatment. The Ganga Action Plan project envisages the gasification of biowastes in digesters for energy production and manurial purposes and treatment of water by aeration before being discharged into the river. Therefore, assessment of biomethanation process in terms of CH₄ production using sewage and other biomass would be of value to understand its economic viability. These consideration led us to attempt the possibility of utilising the sewage and plant biomass for energy conversion at low cost. Water hyacinth or perthenium or mixed biomass like sewage and water hyacinth (or perthenium) were the biomass used.

Most of the digesters in use are meant for the conversion of dung samples like *Gobar*¹ and cost of such digesters is high (Rs. 15000 or more). In spite of heterogeneity, the dung samples are usually available as more or less homogenised slurry, the carbon content of which are high (~10% or ~50% of the total solid).

The plant biomass are usually dispersed in nature and the total solid contents of water hyacinth, perthenium and sewage are approximately 7, 20 and 5% respectively (a little less than 50% is the carbon content). The lignin content of perthenium is very high which renders biomethanation of perthenium difficult under ordinary condition. Water requirement for biogas production is very high, i.e. about 85–90%. Thus, instead of using conventional capital intensive method of energy conversion, a low cost technology for waste management and reuse appear to be desirable. These consideration led us to use low cost portable polyethylenedigesters (Total Energy System, Jagulgachi, South 24-Parganas, West Bengal).

The sewage treatment plant site is the ideal location for commercial production of biogas, as water hyacinth, sewage etc. are available in abundance. The cost of collection and transportation is minimum and the slurry can be discharged to nearby fields and ponds for pisciculture. Hence Bhatpara Sewage Treatment Plant (CMDA, West Bengal) was selected as the site for biogas generation where end-

products could be utilised.

Experimental

Description of the digester: Two polyethylene flat tube digesters made of thick HDPE (11 m long, 1 m lay flat width) (Fig. 1) installed on a wooden support were used for biogas production. The polythene tube was covered with black polyethylene sheet (~1.5–2 mm thickness) and its top with fire-proof and water-proof tarfelt building material (2–2.5 mm thickness). The edges of the digesters were sealed properly with KC2 (Kumar Adhesive P. Ltd., Calcutta) double plus adhesive and the ends of the digesters were sealed to prevent gas-leakage. The total cost of the two digesters including installation and accessories like tubes, earthen ware ring burners, pillow bags for gas collection came out to be approximately Rs. 4000.

Several sets of experiments were performed and the gas production was continued for about two months in each case.

Biogas production from fresh water hyacinth with sewage from the primary sewage settling tank: Fresh water hyacinth from the nearby pond containing enough of sewage was collected and charged as such. Enough sewage

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of plug flow type digester.

from the primary settling tank was added. Addition of inoculum was avoided. Initially sufficient heat was generated. The gas production was found to be low and the water hyacinth was not thoroughly digested even after 2 months. The fact suggest that the outer layer of water hyacinth resisted the microbial attack and it needed proper chopping. However, the water hyacinth content (in terms of solid content) was very low in this experiment.

Gas production using treated water hyacinth alone : Water hyacinth plant was chopped to pieces and its roots were eliminated. Moreover, since the C-content of the fresh water hyacinth is low, enrichment in C-content was made by sun-drying. The sun-dried mass (about 60 kg) was mixed thoroughly in an open tank or earthen vats with inoculum (containing fresh dung samples, oil cake and other ingredients etc.) and little water. They were kept covered for 5–7 days. The slightly digested mass was then charged into the plastic digester with enough water (water from secondary settling tanks of the sewage treatment plants containing little biomass) and fresh inoculum.

The production of biogas (collected in plastic bags) was found to be appreciable in 7 days. The gas production attained a steady state in 12–15 days and became steady for about a month and thereafter decreased. Fresh inoculum was added at regular intervals for maintaining the biogas production.

Biogas production with (i) treated perthenium alone, (ii) treated water hyacinth with sewage and (iii) treated water hyacinth and perthenium (1 : 1) with sewage were carried out similarly as above except sewage from the primary settling tank was added.

A properly filled plastic bag contained sufficient biogas to burn for 40–45 min using low cost earthenware burners. Usually two bags of gas from each plant were collected at an interval of about 10–12 h.

No attempt was made to increase the methane content of the biogas by elimination of CO_2 (by scrubbing). Initially, no analysis was made regarding the CH_4 content of the biogas. Moreover, it was not possible to measure the total quantity of gas evolved during the process. Therefore, no quantitative comparison of the processes could be made. The processes (ii) and (iii) appeared to be more efficient initially but could not be ascertained correctly. The sewage from the primary settling tank (Bhatpara) contained enough Pb^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , grease and surfactants in addition to other impurities. These might hamper biogas production.

However, in order to make a quantitative analysis, the experiment was repeated with treated sun-dried water hyacinth and the biogas was collected at regular intervals of time and analysed for CH_4 using a Netel gas chromatograph. The results indicated that the CH_4 generation in-

creased, became maximum (65–66%) in 20–22 days and decreased thereafter. However, 65% CH_4 does not necessarily mean that the efficiency of conversion was as high as 65%. In fact, this was the result of cumulative accumulation of CH_4 gas when biogas generated contained effectively more CH_4 compared to CO_2 . The subsequent decrease of CH_4 content indicated that the biomethanation process was hampered resulting in more CO_2 production. This was presumably due to the increase of fatty acid concentration and the methanogenic bacteria present in the system was unable to utilise them. The considerable decrease in pH (< 6) substantiated this observation.

Since the total biogas production was not actually measured, an attempt was therefore made for an approximate estimate. The sun-dried water hyacinth contained 18–20% solid mass equivalent to about 9–10% of carbon C-contents for biomethanation. However, the initial and final estimates of C-content of the biomass showed an approximate conversion of about 60% in two months. Thus, 60 kg of sun-dried water hyacinth gave roughly 3.6 kg C-equivalent for biomethanation.

The biogas production was found to increase when water hyacinth was mixed with gobar (about 20%).

Since the retention time for biogas production is usually high and the conversion is moderate, two-stage or multistage digester may be better for biogas production. Two-stage biogas generation had, in fact, been advocated by various authors².

Cost analysis could not made due to lack of adequate experimental data. The cost of the polyethylene digester is low but its life-span under different climatic conditions is not known. It is leak prone but can be rectified easily. Considerable absorption of heat from the sun makes better production of biogas even in winter.

The cost of collection, transportation, chopping, charging of biomass and discharging of the digested slurry cannot be regarded to be negligible as usually assumed. It is true that once charged, it requires a long time before recharging but the process may be made viable by continuously charging the digester with biomass. The value of the manure, i.e. digested slurries, is not known. If the labour cost is minimised considerably and proper utilisation of the manure is made, the biogas production should be quite economical.

Conclusion : An integrated approach for the biogas generation and agriculture from common wastes like sewage, water hyacinth, perthenium etc. using low cost technology should be made. This would help better food production and generate renewable biomass for energy generation. The biogas process can be regarded as eco-friendly and is economically viable as it involves recycling of wastes to generate clean fuel.

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